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Internet Security: A study of the awareness of the threats and measures among Older Adults in Enugu State

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed internet security, focusing on the awareness of the threats and measures among Older Adults in Enugu State. Two research questions guided the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 614,505 older adults in Enugu State. The sample size was 384 older adults comprising of civil servants in Enugu State. The instrument for data collection was researcher - structured questionnaire which was validated by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha statistical tool with grand reliability coefficient value of 0.84. Data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The findings, among others revealed that the extent of awareness of internet security threats among Older adults in Enugu State is low as respondents are unaware that advertisement pop-ups of some free app can lead to download of malicious software that may steal their personal information or damage my device, some installed malicious software from the web can record keystrokes, reveal their password and other personal information to internet scammers, some malicious software disguises itself as helpful but perform its harmful activity in the background such as accessing, changing, blocking or deleting the data upon download, and the difference between http and https URLs. Based on the findings, some recommendations were made among which includes that there is need to provide internet security education for internet users in the state, most especially older adults through the use of loud speaker methods or in their work and worship places such as churches and mosque, among others.

Keywords: awareness, internet security, scareware

INTRODUCTION

Internet Security has become an important area of focus in human security discourse due to the recent expansion of the uses and exponential increase of the users of internet as a result of rapid technological development. Presently, according to Statistical Research Department (2022) about 63.1percent of the world population are on the internet and in Nigeria alone, about 51.0 percent of her population which comprises adults are internet subscribers. These influx of people on the internet poses a new form of security challenge in the name of internet security threats, which exposes the cyber/internet users particularly older adults who depends on the internet for the accomplishment of all manner of tasks (from swift communication, online business transaction, education/online learning, transportation, health care services to access to information etc) to cyber criminals. Nidup (2021) noted that there is high rate of online scam, hacking of websites,

hacking of personal accounts of emails and various social media accounts all of which has caused a huge disruption to individual, groups, offices, organizations, agencies, companies, governments and the countries. Furthermore, Nigeria, earlier in the year 2022, according to Umar-Baba (2022) faced significant cybercrime challenges, ranking 16th globally in a Deloitte report. Also, Kaspersky (2022a) reported that data loss threats, including phishing and scams, increased by 174% with over 1 million detections. Additionally Adepetun (2022) reported that the Nigerian Communications Commission's Computer Security Incident Response Team (NCC-CSIRT) flagged a new malware called HiddenAds which infiltrated the Google Play store by posing as device cleaner apps, which can result to potential issues like malware installation, unintended subscription charges, device performance problems, and privacy risks. These issues emphasize the need for a nationwide awareness campaign to address internet security threats, including in Enugu State, to ensure a high level of internet security

Internet Security basically involves activities to protect oneself and one's activities on the internet. According to Checkpoint (2022), an American-Israeli cyber security organization, Internet security is a central aspect of cybersecurity, and it includes managing cyber threats and risks associated with the Internet, web browsers, web apps, websites and networks. This entails maintaining high level of caution in securing one's activities and personal data and avoiding all manner of threats in a web environment. Internet security is further seen as any cybersecurity measure taken to protect online transactions, data, and activities. Therefore, it is the process of making sure that the person accessing the internet is safe and secure. The main idea behind Internet Security is to protect the user from the internet threats. Therefore, internet security is seen in this study as all the precautionary measures undertaken by internet users to protect their activities, personal information, and web applications such as various social media applications, bank applications and browsers etc. from threats.

On the other hand, threats as it relates to internet or cyber security at large, according to Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) is a potential for violation of security, which exists when there is an entity, circumstance, capability, action, or event that could cause harm. Any circumstance or event with the potential to adversely affect a system through unauthorized access, destruction, disclosure, or modification of data, or denial of service. It is the potential for the exploitation of vulnerability. Hence, these threats results from internal failures, attacks, human errors and sometimes natural catastrophes. Internet security threats are malicious software programs like spyware, adware, trojan horse, bots, viruses and worms etc. which are set up on the system devoid of our information or we can say without any authorization (Bhola, Kaur & Kumar, 2015). Furthermore, University of North Dakota defines internet security threat as any possible malicious attack that seeks to unlawfully access data, disrupt digital operations or damage information. Therefore, contextually, internet security threat is a malicious action with the potential to breach security on the internet, by unlawfully stealing or corrupting data and disruption of an individual's system or device. Some of the most commonest internet security threat according to Allen and Firch (2022); Kaspersky (2022b) include social engineering and malware.

Furthermore, Allen and Firch (2022) see social engineering as a type of threat where threat actors tries to get access to sensitive information by manipulating people into providing sensitive data, account credentials, or granting access to networks or systems. It also refers to as human hacking scams all geared towards luring unaware and careless users to their site and tricking them into inputting personal information, social media login details, financial credentials such as bank account passwords or credit card details among others. Some examples of common social engineering threats experienced by internet users include: Phishing -This is the commonest social engineering threat and according to Nwosu (2022) involves threat actors or criminals posing as a trusted contact and asks an internet user to open a malicious file or link in an email or social media and then persuade him to provide sensitive information including usernames and passwords. An example of phishing involves criminals sending someone an email claiming to be from their financial institution, stating that the person's account's password has been compromised. However, because the email looks legitimate and the message feels urgent, the recipient might quickly click on the included link and input their account information which will then go to the criminal or criminals opening a website that looks like that of an organization but looking closely are often misspelled to scam unsuspecting clients.

Baiting is a type of social engineering threat in which threat actors lure victims into providing sensitive information by promising them something valuable in return. For example, scammers will create pop-up ads that offer free games, music, or movie downloads. If you click on the link, your device will be infected with malware that may steal your personal information; Scareware- It is also known as fraud ware and the threat actors tries to evoke fear in the internet users making them believe their device or system is under imminent threat. Common scareware example is pop-up banners appearing in your browser while surfing the web or in your email, displaying such text such as, "Your computer may be infected with a virus". It either offers to install a software (often malware-infected) for you, or you are supposed to click on a button to either remove the virus that will uninstall the malicious code. But doing so will direct you to a malicious site where your computer becomes infected. Scareware is also spread via spam email that puts up fake warnings, or makes offers for users to buy worthless/harmful services.; and Business Email compromise- This occurs when threat actors use spoof emails to pose as employees or trusted vendors and clients. They'll ask their target to send fraudulent payments, change payroll and direct deposit information, or share sensitive information.

On the other hand, another common threat to internet security is Malware. Malware is the short form of malicious software. According to Computer Information System Company (CISCO) (2023), Malware, short for malicious software, refers to intrusive software developed by cybercriminals with the intent to steal data, damage or destroy computers, and gain unauthorized access. Obotivere and Nwaezeigwe (2020) define malware as any file or programme introduced into a computer with the purpose of causing damage or unauthorized access. Malware can take control of a user's device for various illicit activities such as spamming, monitoring browsing behavior, and displaying unsolicited advertisements based on user activity. Examples of common malware include viruses, which attach themselves to programs, files, or documents and replicate to spread across computers or devices. Worms, on the other hand, are malicious software that self-replicate and spread to other devices or computers without human action. Spyware is malware that monitors a user's activity, collecting personal and financial information without their knowledge. Keyloggers, a type of spyware, record keystrokes to obtain passwords and personal information. Adware, collects data on web usage and displays targeted advertisements, sometimes redirecting browsers to unsafe sites. Trojans masquerade as legitimate software to deceive victims into installing them, enabling malicious activities such as accessing, modifying, or deleting data.

Both social engineering and malware pose risks, however, malware invasion which depends on operating system vulnerability can easily be identified and prevented. On the other hand, social engineering threats that relies on human errors and mistakes made by legitimate users are less predictable and difficult to undo when made. Therefore, it is crucial to raise awareness and educate individuals, particularly older adults who utilizes the internet about internet security threats and practices to prevent such errors.

Internet security is the totality of the strategies, measures, policies, framework, technologies among others geared towards effective and proactive protection from unauthorized access and other unlawful activities of cybercriminals on the internet. Some internet security measures have been identified by various authors and cyber security experts. Some of precautionary measures as according to Coventry, Briggs, Blythe and Tran (2014); Imperva (2022); Kaspersky (2022b) include: having strong passwords and using a secured password manager; using anti-virus programmes and firewalls; running the latest version of a software; logging out of web sites after surfing; using only trusted and secure connections, devices (including Wi-Fi), sites and services; knowing the risks and trying to avoid scam s and phishing; providing minimum personal information such as date of birth, email, phone number, residential address etc to protect identity; being aware of the physical surroundings when online; Use of multifactor authentication; Avoid email from suspicious sources; enable spam filters that hold the emails filters which are deemed as suspicious; Paying attention to the Uniform Resource Locator (URL) of a website to check if they are misspelled as URLs that begin with "https" is an indication that sites are secure rather than "http"; avoid clicking on every link and pop-ups while on the internet; ignoring warning messages asking for an app download and checking if website is encrypted by looking out for the closed padlock icon among others. Awareness of these measures are essential to secured internet usage.

Awareness of these internet security measures will enable internet users, particularly older adults, to avoid human errors that make them vulnerable to threats. From the Chronological perspectives, the United Nations

(UN) refers to a person who is 60+ years as an older adult. On the other hand, the Center for disease control and prevention (CDC) (2015) describes an older adult as a person who is over 65 years old. Most developed countries have accepted the chronological age of 65 years as a definition of 'elderly' or older adult as it is often linked with the age at which they can begin to receive a pension. However, due to low life expectancy of between 50 to 55 in developing countries such as Nigeria, Kowal & Dowd (2001) argues that the chronological age of older adults should be from 50 years and above and in this study, older adults are seen as those from the age of 50 and above.

According to Friemel (2016), Older adults are the fastest growing population among computer and internet users and they use the internet for the convenience it provides in activities ranging from communication, banking, online shopping, aiding self-care and health management to leisure activities like reading the news and getting information on social media and entertainment. Older adults as pointed out by Betts, Hills and Gardner (2019), recognize the benefits that technology provides for staying independent for longer, and many are keen to continue using technology well into older age. Young and older adults, according to LexisNexis (2020) Risk Solutions biannual Cybercrime Report, are the most vulnerable to cyber-attacks, especially those over 75 years because they are less familiar with latest digital technologies and also digital literacy skills, so they are likely to lose money due to their peaking levels of disposable income through cybercrime such as impersonation, consumer fraud, phishing etc. this demands that awareness be raised among these categories of adults to reduce their victimization to cybercrimes in an internet environment.

In the same vein, in Enugu state, there has been an increasing arrest of people involved in internet fraud made by EFCC. According to Manunyi (2022) a compilation of arrests and prosecutions made by the EFCC from January to June, 2022 shows that Enugu alongside Lagos, Ibadan, Abuja, Portharcourt and Benin are the cities that recorded the highest number of internet fraud cases. These cyber-crimes are carried out by the perpetrators because the victims which includes older adults are not aware of the internet threats which exposes them to cyber criminals' nefarious activities. This calls for concerns and bothers the researcher to know the level of awareness of older adults on internet security threats and also, their awareness of measures or practices to protect themselves against falling victims to their activities while using the internet.

In an empirical study, Serianu Agency (2017) carried out Nigeria cybersecurity survey, and reported that, majority of internet users in Nigeria have low awareness of cyberthreats and cybersecurity measures despite their increasingly presence on the internet. In another study, Garba, Othman, and Musa (2020) reported that, majority of university students have low level of awareness of cybersecurity measures and threats. Similarly, Gabra, Sirat, Hajar, and Dauda (2020) reported in their study that majority of university students have low level of awareness of internet threats and internet security measures. In an earlier study, Slusky and Partow-Navid, (2012) reported that students have low awareness of Internet security and engage in poor proactive practices to safeguard their information on the internet. Additionally, Al-Janabi and Al-Shourbaji (2016) reported that, students have low level of awareness of internet security. Though most of the study, showed low awareness of cybersecurity among their respondents, majority of the study were carried out among students, with little or no attention among older adults who are digital migrate thus do not really understand the tricks of cybercriminals like the younger adults.

Recently, cases of older adults falling victim of cybercriminals is increasing among pensioners and older market men and women in Enugu. A case of an older market man whose goods were taken away by cybercriminals who used fake credit alert to purchase goods from his shop is very fresh in the mind of citizens of Enugu State, as the victim slumped and died after discovering what had happened. Another case of a pensioner in Enugu State whose bank account was emptied by cybercriminals is also very fresh in the mind of residents as the prisoner almost loss his live when he slumped in the bank. Every now and then new cases of people losing their entire savings to cybercriminals rents the air. This is not surprising as the number of youths involving in unethical and criminal activities online is increasing daily due to many factors, but not limited to peer group influence, parental irresponsibility, conspicuous spending, among others. From the foregoing discussion, it is imperative to investigate whether the older adults are aware of the different dimensions of internet threats as well as the proactive internet security measures to stay safe online.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to examine the awareness of internet security threats and measures among Adults in Enugu State. However, the specific purposes of the study are to:

1. To find out the extent of awareness of internet security threats among older adults in Enugu state
2. To ascertain the extent of awareness of internet security measures /practices among older adults in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the extent of awareness of internet security threats among adults in Enugu State?
2. What is the extent of awareness of internet security measures among adults in Enugu State?

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population of this study comprised all the older adults (those aged between 50 years -above) in Enugu State which according to the National Population Commission Census (2006), was 418,934 and was projected to 614,505 in 2022 using 0.3% exponential growth rate (City population, 2022). The sample size for the study is 384 older adults who owns smart phones and accesses the internet. The sample size was derived using Meyer (1979) cited in Oribhabor & Anyanwu (2019) sample size determination template, which states that 384 is an appropriate sample size for population size ranging from 500,000 to infinity. To ensure representation of all the older adults in the state in the study, a multi-stage sampling technique was adopted. At the first stage, the cluster sampling technique was employed to cluster the 17 local governments in the state into the three senatorial zones namely: Enugu North, Enugu East and Enugu West. From here, three (3) local government areas each were selected using proportionate stratified sampling. The reason for using this sampling technique was to select the local governments with the highest population in each zones and they include: Nsukka, Igbo-Eze North, Igbo-Etiti (Enugu North), Enugu East, Enugu North, Enugu South (Enugu East), Awgu, Ezeagu and Udi (Enugu West). Then 55, 35, 44, 42, 35, 43, 43, 37, and 50 respondents who are civil servants working in the local government secretariats were proportionately allocated to the selected local government area. Hence, those with lesser population were allocated lesser respondents and vice versa. At the final stage, purposive sampling was also employed to ensure that only those that possess smart mobile phones or accesses the internet were part of the selected respondents.

Two research questions were posed and the researcher developed a structured questionnaire titled: Internet Security: A study of the awareness of the threats and measures among older adults (IS:ATMOL). The questionnaire was made up of 20 items divided into clusters A and B. The respondents were required to choose one from the list of items- Very Highly Aware, Highly Aware, Lowly Aware and Very Lowly Aware with mean rating scale of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively, which represent their opinion on the statement made in Cluster A and B respectively. When answering the research question, an item with a calculated mean value equal to or greater than 2.50 (2.50 -4.00) was accepted as high awareness, while the calculated mean of an item less than 2.50 was regarded as low awareness. The questionnaire was face validated by three lecturers of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka- Two from the Department of Adult Education & Extra -Mural Studies and one from the Department of Science Education. The Cronbach alpha method was used to test for reliability of the instrument. To do this, 20 copies of the instrument was distributed to civil servant who met the stipulated requirement in chosen local governments in Ebonyi state. Upon analyzing their responses, a general coefficient of 0.84 was obtained, which is high and adequate for the study. The questionnaire was distributed to civil servants who fall within the stipulated age range and possess devices, such as a smart cell phone required to access the internet and were all collected.

RESULTS

The data collected for the study was analyzed and presented according to the research Questions guiding the study. A total of 384 copies of questionnaires were distributed and collected from the sampled respondents,

however, 2 copies were not correctly filled and as such were discarded thus, a total of 382 copies, representing 99.5% were used for the study.

Research Question 1: *What is the extent of awareness of internet security threats among adults in Enugu State?*

Table 1: Mean analysis on the extent of awareness of internet security threats among older adults

S/N	Items Statement	VHA	HA	LA	VLA	Mean	St.D	Decision
1	I'm aware that scammers can imitate emails of organization to pose as trusted employers for fraudulent purposes.	119	103	47	113	2.60	1.20	Highly Aware
2	I'm aware that some email messages may contain harmful attachments.	156	33	111	82	2.69	1.21	Highly Aware
3	I'm aware that advertisement pop-ups of some free app can lead to download of malicious software that may steal my personal information or damage my device	36	54	196	96	2.08	0.87	Lowly Aware
4	I'm aware that my personal information can be stolen by clicking some malicious links on social media.	121	98	139	24	2.83	0.95	Highly Aware
5	I'm aware that some of the pop-up warnings about my device being under threat are fake, a trick to click and download harmful software that may steal my personal information.	75	149	89	69	2.60	0.99	Highly Aware
6	I'm aware that some installed malicious software from the web can record keystrokes, reveal my password and other personal information to internet scammers	38	51	189	104	2.06	0.89	Lowly Aware
7	I'm aware that some malicious software disguises itself as helpful but perform its harmful activity in the background such as accessing, changing, blocking or deleting the data upon download.	47	59	137	139	2.04	1.00	Lowly Aware
8	I'm aware that malicious software collects information on your web usage, so as to automatically display, download appropriate advertisement on your devices and redirect your browser to unsafe sites.	40	112	186	44	2.39	0.83	Lowly Aware
9	I'm aware of the difference between http and https URLs	53	102	152	75	2.35	0.94	Lowly Aware
	Grand Mean					2.40	0.99	Lowly Aware

Results from table 1 above shows the responses of older adults (50 years and above) on their extent of awareness of internet security threats. From the results; majority of the respondents agreed to item 1, 2, 4 and 5 with mean ranging from 2.60 to 2.83 which indicates that they are highly aware that, scammers can imitate emails of organization to pose as trusted employers for fraudulent purposes, some email messages may contain harmful attachments, their personal information can be stolen by clicking some malicious links on social media, and some of the pop-up warnings about my device being under threat are fake, a trick to click

and download harmful software that may steal my personal information. on the other hand, items 3, 6, 7, 8, and 9 with mean ranging from 2.04 - 2.39 indicates that respondents are lowly aware that; advertisement pop-ups of some free app can lead to download of malicious software that may steal their personal information or damage my device, some installed malicious software from the web can record keystrokes, reveal their password and other personal information to internet scammers, some malicious software disguises itself as helpful but perform its harmful activity in the background such as accessing, changing, blocking or deleting the data upon download, and the difference between http and https URLs. Overall, the grand mean of 2.40 shows that majority of the older adults have low awareness of internet security threats.

Research Question 2: *What is the extent of awareness of internet security measures among adults in Enugu State?*

Table 2: Mean analysis on the extent of awareness of measures of internet security among older adults.

S/N	Items Statement	VHA	HA	LA	VLA	Mean	St.D	Decision
1	Avoid downloading free unverified software from the internet as some may secretly contain malware.	107	70	119	86	2.52	1.12	Highly Aware
2	Use of anti-virus programmes and firewalls.	77	92	189	24	2.58	0.87	Highly Aware
3	Use of multi-factor authentication	55	81	142	104	2.23	1.00	Lowly Aware
4	Avoid email from suspicious sources	128	55	117	82	2.60	1.15	Highly Aware
5	Enable spam filters that hold the emails filters which are deemed as suspicious.	91	101	114	76	2.54	1.06	Highly Aware
6	Check Uniform Resource Locator (URL) of a website to know if they are misspelt as "http" instead of "https" which is an indication that sites are secure.	31	98	142	111	2.13	0.92	Lowly Aware
7	Avoid clicking on every link and pop-ups while on the internet.	121	97	109	55	2.74	1.05	Highly Aware
8	Ignoring warning messages asking for an app download	133	48	89	112	2.53	1.23	Highly Aware
9	Using strong password	125	139	24	94	2.77	1.15	Highly Aware
10	Always checking if website is encrypted by looking out for the closed padlock icon.	81	19	197	85	2.25	1.02	Lowly Aware
11	Avoid inputting sensitive information in unverified websites	115	102	71	94	2.62	1.15	Highly Aware
	Grand Mean					2.48	1.67	Lowly Aware

Results from table 2 shows the responses of older adults (50 years and above) on their level of awareness of measures of internet security. From the results; items 1,2, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, and 11, which indicates that, the older adults are highly aware of internet security measures such as: avoid downloading free unverified software from the internet as some may secretly contain malware, use of anti-virus programmes and firewalls, avoiding email from suspicious sources, avoid clicking on every link and pop-ups while on the internet, Ignoring warning messages asking for an app download, Using strong password, and Avoid inputting sensitive information in unverified websites. On the other hand, items 3, 6, and 10 with mean ranging from 2.13-2.25 indicates that, majority of older adults have low awareness of internet security measures such as use of multi-factor authentication, checking Uniform Resource Locator (URL) of a website to know if they

are misspelt as “http” instead of “https” which is an indication that sites are secure, and Always checking if website is encrypted by looking out for the closed padlock icon. The overall grand mean of 2.48, shows that majority of the older adults have low awareness of internet security measures.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that, majority of the older adults in Enugu State have low awareness of internet threats. This is because majority of the older adults are less aware that; advertisement pop-ups of some free app can lead to download of malicious software that may steal their personal information or damage my device, some installed malicious software from the web can record keystrokes, reveal their password and other personal information to internet scammers, some malicious software disguises itself as helpful but perform its harmful activity in the background such as accessing, changing, blocking or deleting the data upon download, and the difference between http and https URLs. The findings is in accordance with the findings of Serianu Agency (2017) which reported that, majority of internet users which include older adults in Nigeria have low awareness of cyberthreats despite their increasingly presence on the internet. The different techniques the older adults are less aware of, are frequently used technique among cybercriminals, thus, older adults having less awareness of these technique is a case to worry about.

The findings of the study revealed that older adults are less aware of internet security measures to combat cyberthreats. This is not surprising as majority of the older adults are just adopting the use of internet for different purposes and might not understand how to stay safe online. it was revealed that the older adults are less aware that, the use of multi-factor authentication, checking Uniform Resource Locator (URL) of a website to know if they are misspelt as “http” instead of “https” which is an indication that sites are secure, and always checking if website is encrypted by looking out for the closed padlock icon are proactive internet security measures. The findings relate to the findings of Garba, Othman, and Musa (2020) which found out that students have low awareness of cybersecurity measures. When students have low awareness of cybersecurity measures it is not surprising that older adults who are mostly civil servants and pensioners have low awareness. The findings of the study also correspond with the earlier findings of Al-Janabi and Al-Shourbaji (2016) which found out that their respondents have low awareness of internet security measures to stay safe on the internet.

CONCLUSION

The study examined the awareness of internet security threats and measures among Adults in Enugu State. Every user of the internet is expected to be aware of threats on the internet and how to stay safe from the various threats on the internet, thus, any user of the internet who is not aware of internet threats and the proactive internet security measures is sitting on a timed bomb. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that, older adults in Enugu State have low awareness of internet security threats, most especially the dubious technique of using app pop-ups to collect personal information of internet users, ransom wares, and sharing of virus. The study also concluded that, the older adults are less aware of the most effective internet security measures such as the use of multi-factor authentication, verifying websites before logging in, and understanding how secure a site is, before using it for transactions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were suggested based on the findings of the study:

- c. There is need to provide internet security education for internet users in the state, most especially older adults through the use of loud speaker methods or through worship places such as churches and mosque.
- d. The National Orientation Agency (NOA) in collaboration with EFCC should organize periodic public internet security threat awareness campaign for internet users in the state, most especially civil servants, pensioners, market men and women

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